

1 **The serum transcriptome in chronic HBV.**

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6 These cells were defined by expression of *Gpr108* and *Gpr174*. The cells expressed a suite of Siglec
7 receptors including *Siglec7*, *Siglec10* and *Siglec5*, with *Nkg7* which appeared to function in concert with
8 *CD33*.

9 Citations

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